

**CHANGE IN FOOD CONSUMPTION BEHAVIOUR - WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO
ONLINE FOOD PURCHASE IN TIRUNELVELI**

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ABSTRACT

People are more regular to dine-in at restaurant for their meals, but after Covid 19 there is a change in the behavior of food consumption among people. People prefer to purchase food through online food delivery apps. The online food ordering system provides convenience for the customers. This study primarily focuses on the factors that influence them towards online food purchase. The sample of 55 respondents around Tirunelveli city is taken as the sample size for purpose of study. The result indicates that they choose online food for their convenience instead of going to restaurants. Respondents say that they are satisfied with the content available through online ordering portal. Majority of the respondents say that they face problems like poor packaging

Keywords: online food ordering, reasons, level of satisfaction, problems

INTRODUCTION

Online Food ordering system is a process in which one can order various foods and beverages from some local restaurant and hotels through the use of internet, just by sitting at home or any place. And the order is delivered to the told location. Everyone is having busy schedule whether it is urban area or rural. As these days women are no less than men, in any field. So in big cities even wives are working women, therefore mostly the small families manage to have their food ordered from somewhere, as they lack time. So food ordering system these days has one of the fastest growing market, though being a new idea. In this project we have developed something like the same to earn from and serve the nation in a much better way possible. Nowadays, people are more regular to dine-in at restaurant for their meals. The online food ordering system provides convenience for the customers that are nothing special but the general busy people of the society.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Ram Kumar B P (2022) in his study he concluded that that all the customers use food apps in today's day and age because of its rapid response. It enhance my understanding of people's preferences, the efficacy in time management, affordability, food preferences, discounts available and door-to-door service without compromising on quality.

Jyotishman Das (2018) in his study he explained that The factors that encourages consumers the most is Doorstep Delivery followed by Ease & Convenience . Consumers are mostly influenced when they receive any Rewards & Cashbacks followed by Location.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The main objective of this study is

- To find out the respondent’s perception & knowledge about online food ordering that influences their buying decisions.
- To analyze the factors that influences the consumer’s perception towards online food delivery apps.
- To find the most popular app in the digital food delivery system.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The questionnaire is prepared on Google form for collecting primary data and journals, articles, Internet etc. used as secondary data. Descriptive research design is conducted for studying and analyzing consumer perception towards online food ordering apps around Tirunelveli city. The sample of 55 respondents around Tirunelveli city is taken as the sample size for purpose of study. The technique used to decide on sample size was convenient sampling technique. Major tool is used in the analysis process has been Simple percentage, weighted average method, garrett ranking method , graphs and chart for interpreting the data collected.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Up to 20 years	33	60%
	21 to 30 years	21	38%
	31 to 40 years	01	02%
Gender	Male	28	51%
	Female	27	49%
Marital status	Married	15	27%
	Unmarried	40	73%
Type of family	Joint family	40	73%
	Nuclear family	15	27%

Educational Qualification	SSLC	02	04%
	12 th	10	18%
	UG	38	69%
	PG	05	09%
Monthly family income	Less than 20000	22	49%
	Rs 20000 – Rs 40000	13	29%
	Rs 40000 - Rs 60000	09	20%
	More than Rs 60000	01	02%
Respondents' preference over food app	Zomato	38	69%
	Swiggy	15	27%
	Uber eats	02	04%
Source of information about online food delivery	Newspaper	01	02%
	Internet	25	46%
	Advertisement	10	18%
	Friends	14	26%
	Family members	05	09%
Which meal typically orders online?	Dinner	21	38%
	Snacks	21	38%
	Lunch	12	22%
	Breakfast	01	02%
What occasion respondents order online	Special occasion	17	31%
	Get together	18	33%
	Don't want to cook	20	37%
Spend money for ordering food per time	Less than 150	06	11%
	150-250	18	33%
	251-500	22	40%

	500 above	09	16%
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Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

- ❖ Majority of the respondents belong to the age group of less than 20 years.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents are male.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents are unmarried.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents belong to joint family.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents are graduates.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents have a monthly income of less than Rs 20000.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents prefer Zomato.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents get information about online food delivery from Internet.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents order food for their dinner and they order mostly when they don't want to cook.
- ❖ Majority of the respondents spend nearly Rs 251 – Rs 250 for purchasing online food.

REASON FOR CHOOSING ONLINE FOOD

S.No	Statement	5	4	3	2	1	Total score	Avg score	Rank
1	Lack of time to cook	13 (65)	22 (88)	15 (45)	3 (6)	2 (2)	206	3.74	2
2	Convenient to experience instead of going to restaurant	14 (70)	28 (112)	11 (33)	2 (4)	0 (0)	219	3.98	1
3	Economical & more convenient	7 (35)	25 (100)	19 (57)	3 (6)	1 (1)	199	3.61	4
4	Offers/ discounts/ coupons available	10 (50)	25 (100)	15 (35)	3 (6)	2 (2)	203	3.69	3

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION:

The above table explains the reason for choosing online food. Majority of the respondents say that they choose online food for their convenience instead of going to restaurants, followed by lack of time to

cook and attractive offers/ discounts and coupons available.

LEVEL OF SATISFACTION

S.no	Statement	5	4	3	2	1	Total score	Avg score	Rank
1	Satisfied with the content available through online ordering portal	13 (65)	27 (108)	13 (39)	2 (4)	0 (0)	216	3.92	1
2	Satisfied with qualities of food delivered	11 (55)	27 (108)	15 (45)	2 (4)	0 (0)	212	3.85	3
3	Satisfied with overall process of online ordering of food	9 (45)	29 (116)	16 (48)	1 (2)	0 (0)	211	3.83	4
4	Didn't face any problem(issue) while using online portal	10 (50)	17 (68)	20 (60)	6 (12)	2 (2)	192	3.49	7
5	Satisfied with wide choice of food	11 (55)	20 (80)	23 (69)	1 (2)	0 (0)	206	3.74	5
6	Satisfied with behaviour of staff during delivery	13 (65)	23 (92)	18 (54)	1 (2)	0 (0)	213	3.87	2
7	Accurate delivery to mentioned location	9 (45)	24 (96)	17 (51)	5 (10)	0 (0)	202	3.67	6

The above table explains the level of satisfaction of the respondents towards online food delivery services. Majority of the respondents say that they are satisfied with the content available through online ordering portal followed by that they are satisfied with behaviour of staff during delivery and Satisfied with qualities of food delivered

PROBLEM FACED BY CUSTOMER WHILE ORDERING FOOD THROUGH ONLINE

S.No	Statement	1 (75)	2 (60)	3 (50)	4 (39)	5 (24)	Total respondents	Total Score	Avg score	Rank
1	Quantity	17	21	8	6	3	55	3241	58.90	2

		(1275)	(1260)	(400)	(234)	(72)				
2	Packaging	19	20	8	6	2	55	3307	60.10	1
		(1425)	(1200)	(400)	(234)	(48)				
3	Delivery time	17	17	13	6	2	55	3227	58.67	3
		(1275)	(1020)	(650)	(234)	(48)				
4	Food quality	10	19	16	7	3	55	3035	55.18	4
		(750)	(1140)	(800)	(273)	(72)				
5	Wrong delivery of foods	10	12	10	9	14	55	2657	48.3	5
		(750)	(720)	(500)	(351)	(336)				

Source: Primary Data

INTERPRETATION:

Garrett Ranking method is used to analyse the problem faced by the respondent while ordering food through online. The above table explains the problems faced by the respondents while ordering food through online. Majority of the respondents say that they face problems like poor packaging followed by poor quantity and delayed delivery time. Some time the food may get spilled, the quantity may be very less than we expect and the food may not reach us on time that may lead us to frustration.

CONCLUSION

To conclude this research on change in behavior of food consumption, it is thus inferred that a majority of people use food apps as it's the best way to save time and is convenient. The study conducted has given an overview of change in behavior of food consumption among people around Tirunelveli city which has quite positive output. Furthermore, ordering via food apps is a precise operation. Among the respondents, the most preferred is cash on delivery and it is the safest and most secure form of payment. The study discloses that youngsters are more inclined to online food and the main reason is offers and discounts. The study also states that all age and income groups use food apps, and they are happy with the service quality, hygiene, and packaging system, which make people order from food apps.

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